

D.6.4. Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising activities

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING ROLES tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
Task 8.1	Target audiences, strategy, dissemination objectives
Task 8.4	Online media presence

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GEARING ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
E-UC	End-User Community
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document provides guidance and suggestions about the development of innovative tools and materials in video and audio form, in the GEARING-Roles Project, which will be posted online to reach a broader audience. Moreover, this deliverable provides information on the media infographics, photos and videos that may be used in offline and online settings during the awareness raising activities. In light of this, this deliverable is a “living” document, which will be updated a number of times throughout the project. The specific objectives include:

- (i) maximise visibility and raise awareness of the project and its activity to target stakeholders and the wider public;
- (ii) engage target groups and key actors across project activities;
- (iii) share information and raise awareness about challenging problems and solutions with regard to gender equality.

1. Gender Sensitive print media for awareness raising

- Online and print media will be disseminated to target stakeholders to maintain awareness of the project results and
- Online promotional campaigns will be launched throughout the duration of the project, exploiting the latest trends and functions of social media while utilising visually appealing graphic designs. Ad campaigns will be launched to increase visibility amongst targeted groups. A solid and appealing Visual Identity has been designed:
 - to shape the project's brand, reflecting its core values and
 - to visually assist targeting of key messages to ensure that throughout the 4 years of operation of the GEARING Roles project the members of the project consortium can prepare their communication materials in a coherent way. The key messages to be conveyed revolve around the aim of increasing general sensitivity, understanding and knowledge about gender (in)equality.

Booklet

The GEARING Booklet discusses the project's aim and activities. The booklet has been initially produced in English but it will be translated to relevant national languages and be used for distribution to public audiences, at scientific meetings, and for the commercial and social interests in gender awareness raising activities (e.g. infodays, conferences, teaching, workshops...), and to other relevant stakeholders. It will also be available in electronic format via for download from the project website. In years 3 and 4, summaries of major findings, achievements and policy recommendations will be produced and tailored to target audiences.

For the layout of the initial project booklet see the Visual Guide in Appendix 1.

Figure 1: Booklet first draft.

Infographics

Pictures, info graphics, and audiovisual materials are important communication tools to influence perceptions, attitudes and social change, particularly among young people and students who are key stakeholders within GEARING Roles. In light of this, the EIGE guide on gender awareness raising principles of gender-sensitive language for written and oral communications will be applied to audio and visual materials (EIGE 2018) within the project. Therefore, GEARING Roles project will ensure that:

- Both women and men will be visible and treated equally in media outputs and project messages.
- Gender stereotypes are challenged and fought through the use of appropriate language and images.

Roll up & Poster

The project roll-up and the poster templates will be produced for presentation at project's own events as well as for external conferences and workshops. The roll-up template is available from the outset of the project, open to be tailored to the partners' communication goals in local languages, using Adobe Illustrator or other professional publishing tools. The poster template, in Power Point, will allow partners to present results related to Gearing Roles at conferences and workshops, tailoring the content to the target audience.

Figure 2: Project Poster

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Factsheet

The factsheet includes factual information about the project like its acronym and full title, start date, duration, funding and contact information along with the project's abstract.

Figure 3: Factsheet draft

2. Gender Sensitive audio-visual media for awareness raising

Within the project, a key objective is the deconstruction of gender roles. The project aims to do this by raising awareness of what these gender roles are and how internalised and unchallenged behaviours, perceptions, and practices related to gender and what this means, perpetuate gender inequalities. The GEAR tool illustrates how implicit bias operates, and encourages organisations to challenge cultural stereotypes and reconsider the reasons behind individual and institutional decisions. With this in mind, GEARING-Roles considers that a viable approach to tackling implicit bias is to understand the sociology and psychology of gender roles, challenge them, and move towards eliminate their effects on equality. GEARING roles will thus, reinforce a gender-sensitive perspective in research, and research institutions, including in their every-day teaching and campus life.

In order to achieve these goals, GEARING Roles will develop three actions:

1. Identify, gather and collect existing initiatives and good practices undertaken by project partners, and other projects to raise awareness on gender roles and gender equality through the use of multi-media. These materials will be shared in the Project social media channels and/or Project YouTube channel. Besides, these videos could be used for teaching and fostering gender mainstreaming in research.

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-Examples:

- INSPIRA Video: <https://youtu.be/-ShBktgkHxk>
 - UDEUSTO gender Interdisciplinary platform: <https://youtu.be/G3WJSy1HSn0>
 - OBU videos: <https://www.brookes.ac.uk/research/work-life-experiences/>
2. Focus on advocacy activities in campuses and outside to mobilise support from different stakeholders. GEARING-Roles will identify and gathered relevant innovative materials and resources to raise awareness about gender equality. In particular, it will discuss the causes and consequences of the limited representation of female leaders in decision-making boards and selection committees, while at the same time, highlighting examples of best practices in European institutions. Resources and efforts will be also directed towards awareness raising activities and the training of key and relevant stakeholders, further strengthening our networks and alliances in the implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).
 3. Develop our own resources to be shared online and displayed on wide screens at events. They will include:
 - project storytelling: explaining aims and objectives of the project in an engaging and accessible way. Storytelling is a powerful tool for inspiring action and change and influencing thought leaders, funders, decision makers and especially young people. In the digital era, the shape and delivery of stories has shifted dramatically. Effective storytelling will inspire audiences, particularly young people, by creating human connection and emotional resonance with gender topics. Stories can be used to share lessons learnt, successes and failures with other actors and key audiences. These materials can be easily integrated in both teaching, disseminating and community engagement activities
 - Develop short informational videos on gender-related data, based on the literature review conducted in WP3's environment and cultural assessment, which will be uploaded on social media platforms. Moreover, learning experiences, progress, challenges, and strategies of the project will also be presented.

Annex I – Booklet First Draft

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6 Gender Equality Plans in 6 Research institutions

Challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers, to create real institutional change.

The GEARING-Roles project, is an EU funded project under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme, grant agreement No. 824536.

INTRODUCTION

Gender Equality is a fundamental human rights, as well as a Sustainable Development Goal. Despite this, women across Europe still suffer from a lack of equality and gender violence has become widespread. Academia and research is no exception to this.

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that will bring together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans in 6 organizations (5 Universities and 1 Research Funding Organization) applying the criteria established and tested by GEAR-tool developed by the European Commission.

Leadership Foundation- Uk, AESIS - The Netherlands, GARAGE ERASMUS - Italy, AERNOVA- Spain, IFEES - USA
GEDC - USA, CIG- Portugal, VITA ACTIVA - Slovenia, EDIW- Italy, EMAKUNDE - Spain, UNIBASQ - Spain, Estonian
Ministry Education and Research - Estonia, VELATIA- Spain, Mujeres por Africa - Spain, Dutch Network of
Women Professors - The Netherlands, Unidad de mujer y Ciencia -Spain, UNICA- Belgium,
SCIENCE Business - Belgium, SANTANDER - Spain, GEDII, GENERA,SAGE,PLOTINA

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Female Career Progression: To remove barriers, to female recruitment and devise Personal Career Development Plans

Education and Research: to provide alternative references in traditionally male dominated areas (STEM) and in those where women are majority but kept under glass ceilings (Health& Care, Hum, Law, SSCC in general) by strengthening the gender dimension in research programs and methodologies, fostering gender- knowledge and scientific production in relation to gender and feminist studies, and by reinforcing women researchers' careers

Leadership and Decision Making: To address gender imbalances, in the representation, processes and the promotion of leadership in research institutions

Promotion of Gender Equality in Research Organisations and key stakeholders for the reinforcement of ERA: disseminate the common framework and outputs for institutional gender assessment, planning, monitoring and evaluation to establish commitment to gender equality in major European stakeholder organisations and build a sustainable long-term network of organisations advancing gender equality

A Gender Equality Plan (GEP) is a set of actions aiming at:

- Conducting impact assessment/audits
- Identifying and implementing innovative strategies to correct any bias
- Setting targets and monitoring progress via indicators(European Commission, 2012)

STEPS OF THE PROCESS

TIMELINE

- Kick-off/Final event
- Pairing event
- Consortium Meeting
- Annual conference
- Training

PROJECT ACTIVITIES

TRAINING

- Train participating institutions on how to develop researcher career development strategies embedded in the general gender equality plans.
- Design general and topic-specific training programmes on gender equality, building capacities to address main GEPs' areas of action

MENTORING

- Develop a mentoring programme pilot for R2 (post-docs) female researchers to support them in their career progression

PROMOTION OF GENDER EQUALITY

- Promote gender mainstreaming in research by including a gender perspective in research programs and methodologies and by fostering scientific production in relation to gender and feminist studies.
 - Support awareness raising and behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership.
 - Promote community engagement in the promotion of diversity and inclusion outside the classroom and among different members on campus.
 - Promote gender equality through dissemination and outreach activities such as campaigns, videos, blogs and podcasts
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EVALUATION

- Evaluate the design of consortium partners GEPs, defining and fine-tuning guidelines and KPIs for their evaluation in collaboration with consortium partners.
- Analyse the overall impact of the implementation of GEPs in addressing gender inequality among participating consortium members based on indicators set with partners and general measures of gender equality.

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